

Knowledge, Attitude and Practices Towards Modifiable Risk Factors for Hypertension Among Civil Servants in Akure Municipality, Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated knowledge, attitude and practices towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure municipality, Ondo State, Nigeria. A workplace population study which was a cross-sectional descriptive study of survey design was carried out in Akure the capital city of the State. The study population comprised of civil servants between the ages of 18-60 years in Ondo State. It was conducted among 500 consenting urban civil servants recruited randomly selected from 7 ministries, and agencies in Akure municipality. A close ended questionnaire containing 45 items was the tool for data collection and it was composed of 4 sections. Validity of the instrument was done by giving the draft of the questionnaire to experts in health education to vet. The reliability of the questionnaire was done with a coefficient of 0.72 which indicated that the instrument had good internal consistency and was adequate for the study. However, only 480 of the selected respondents returned usable questionnaire. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that respondents had poor knowledge, average positive attitude and average good practices toward hypertension. It was recommended among others that measures should be taken by health providers to improve the knowledge and practice towards hypertension of this study population. Appropriate workplace interventions need to be

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developed and implemented to reduce the preventable burden of hypertension.

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Introduction

The mortality and morbidity rate of hypertension is high and it sets a main public health problem globally, adding significantly to the world-wide disease, burden of heart disease, kidney failure, premature death, stroke, and disability, (Angaw, Dadi & Alene, 2015). Hypertension is often referred to as a silent killer as an outcome of its asymptomatic nature which makes the findings hard in several persons (American Heart Association, 2017). Certain physical qualities and choice of one's way of life can put a person at higher risk for high blood pressure. When left untreated, the harm that high blood pressure causes to the circulatory system is important contributing factor to heart attack, stroke and other health threats.

High blood pressure also referred to as hypertension is the pressure of blood in the arteries - the vessels that transmit blood from the heart to the brain and other parts of the body. An actual amount of pressure is required to acquire the blood round the body. The beat at which the heart pumps blood is based on the flow of blood. The burden of the heart does not remain at equal level at all times. It differs based on doings at a specific point in time. Hypertension happens as an outcome to lengthy duration of irregular pressure of the main arteries (Delacroix, Chokka, Worthley, 2018). Hypertension means that the blood pressure in a person is steadily greater than the recommended level. It is commonly defined in adults as systolic blood pressure higher than or equal to 140mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure higher than or equal to 90mmHg.

The modifiable risk factors are behavioural risk factors that can be reduced or controlled by intervention, these includes physical inactivity or lack of exercise, smoking or tobacco use, alcohol consumption and unhealthy diet and feeding, poor rest or sleep, stress and lack of medical check-up (WHO, 2018). WHO (2018) gave tobacco use, physical inactivity, alcohol, and unhealthy diet as the four main behavioural factors related to hypertensions. Other factors that can result based on the modifiable risk factors are high cholesterol level, elevated glucose, overweight and obesity. The modifiable risk factors of hypertensions are known to increase the likelihood of high blood pressure and are related to lifestyle of individuals. The risk factors of tobacco use, harmful use of alcohol, insufficient physical activity, overweight/obesity, unhealthy diet, high cholesterol level and high blood sugar could lead to hypertension (Jaya, 2020).

Worldwide available population-based observational studies, offered a sweeping view of the worldwide pressure of hypertension as the heading preventable cause of death worldwide. The authors valued that in 2010, the global prevalence of hypertension was 1.39 billion people, representing 31% of all grown-ups. This represented a 5.2% rise in the worldwide prevalence between 2000 and 2010. (Mills, Kelly, Reed, Kearney, Bundy, Reynolds, 2016). It is assessed that hypertension affects about 1 billion people all over the biosphere and it is the key risk factor for many other cardiovascular diseases (Mills, et al., 2016).

Nigeria is not exempted from this rising threat. Hypertension is greatly prevalent in Nigeria as in other African countries and creates the key danger factor for stroke in the country. One in every 5 Nigerian grown-ups has high blood pressure, less than a third of those with high blood pressure are aware of the fact that they have hypertension and less than a third of those who are aware are undergoing any form of treatment and less than a third of those undergoing treatment are sufficiently controlled (Ekeh, Ogunniyi, Isamade & Ekrikpo 2015).

A significant population group such as, the public servants, whose type of job encourages sedentary behaviour joined with unwholesome dietary practices are at a larger

risk of emerging obesity which is an important donor to the increasing burden of hypertension (Aladeniyi, Adeniyi, Fawole, Adeolu, Goon & Ajayi, 2017). In a study conducted by Aladeniyi, et al. in Ondo State among public civil servants, result displayed that there was a high prevalence of hypertension amid study members with great hypertension unawareness (72%), while only 28% were aware of their hypertension status.

A person's knowledge of blood pressure play important role in the skill to avert hypertension. Avoidance of hypertension is attainable if the knowledge of its modifiable risk factors is better and this could lead to avoidance of its complications. Epidemiological studies have shown that a stroke does not happen at random, there are modifiable risk factors which lead to stroke, therefore awareness and good knowledge of these risk factors are very vital to its prevention.

The burden of hypertension is increasing and an important contributor to it is the increasing burden of obesity. Several persons have a chance of growing obesity, and some are mostly at a larger risk. A significant population group are the civil servants, whose nature of job promotes sedentary deeds joined with unwholesome dietary practices and subsequently, obesity (Aladeniyi et al. 2017). Civil servants establish a great percentage of a nation's workforce and they add significantly to the economic growth of a nation yet they are not secure of the scourge of hypertension. The attention of hypertension has always been on hospitalised patients, the supposition that asymptomatic persons are strong is doubtful. In the light of this, this study examined the attitude, knowledge, and practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among apparently well persons working in Ondo State Civil Service Commission.

Evaluation of attitude, knowledge, and practices (KAP) is a vital element of hypertension control, but slight info is obtainable from developing countries particularly in Ondo State where hypertension has recently been known as a main public health problem. Since involvements in workplace locations are measured to be cost-effective in averting cardiovascular diseases having hypertension as its main danger factor. Hence, the study examined attitude, knowledge, and practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension amid apparently healthy persons working in Ondo State Civil Service Commission.

Based on the foregoing, this study investigated attitude, knowledge, and practices towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure municipality, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. knowledge of modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality;
- ii. attitude towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality;
- iii. practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality;
- iv. relationship between knowledge and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension;
- v. relationship between attitude and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension; and
- vi. relationship between practice and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study

1. What is the knowledge of modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality in Ondo State?
2. What is the attitude towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality in Ondo State?
3. What is the practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality in Ondo State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were generated for this study

1. There is no significant relationship between knowledge and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.
2. There is no significant relationship between attitude and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.
3. There is no significant relationship between practice and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

Methodology

A workplace population study which was a cross-sectional descriptive study of survey design was carried out in Akure the capital city of the State. The study population comprised of civil servants between the ages of 18-60 years in Ondo State. It was conducted among 500 consenting urban civil servants recruited randomly selected from 7 ministries, and agencies in Akure municipality with the official working hours between 8:00am to 4:00pm, to produce a representative sample of the workforce in the city. All pregnant civil servants during the period of study were excluded.

A close ended questionnaire containing 45 items was the tool for data collection and it was composed of 4 sections. The first section was designed to elicit data on the participants' demographic characteristics, the second was on knowledge on modifiable risk factors for hypertension, the third section on the attitude towards risk factors for hypertension which was measured with Likert-type scale of frequently, sometimes, rarely and never, while the fourth was on practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension. Validity of the instrument was done by giving the draft of the questionnaire to experts of health education to vet.

The reliability of the questionnaire was done with a coefficient of 0.72 which indicated that the instrument had good internal consistency and was adequate for the study. However, only 480 of the selected respondents returned usable questionnaire. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentages while inferential statistics of Chi-Square was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Chi-square was used to test for association between socio-demographic variables and Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of the respondents.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the knowledge of modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality in Ondo State?

Table 1: Knowledge of modifiable risk factors for Hypertension

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor	354	73.8
Good	126	26.3

Findings from table 1 above shows that only (26.3%) of the study subjects had good knowledge towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension, while (73.8%) had poor

knowledge. Figure i further revealed the knowledge towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension at a glance

Figure i: Bar Chart showing knowledge towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension

Research Question 2: What is the attitude towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality in Ondo State?

Table 2: Attitude towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension

Attitude	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Negative	297	38.1
Positive	183	61.9

The result from the table above shows that more than half of the respondents (61.9%) had positive attitude towards modifiable risk factors of hypertension. Figure ii further revealed the attitude towards risk factors for hypertension at a glance

Figure ii: Bar Chart showing attitude relating to modifiable risk factors for hypertension

Research Question 3: What is the practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension among civil servants in Akure Municipality in Ondo State?

Table 3: Practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension

Practice	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor	227	47.3

Good	253	52.7
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Findings from table 3 show that a little above half of the respondents (52.7%) had good practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension. Figure iii further revealed the practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension at a glance.

Figure iii: Bar Chart showing practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between knowledge and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

	KNOWLEDGE SCORE			Chi-Square	P-Value
	Good	Poor	Total		
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		
Age					
<30	39(43.3)	51(56.7)	90(100.0)	18.241	0.001*
30-39	41(25.6)	119(74.4)	160(100.0)		
≥40	46(20.0)	184(80.0)	230(100.0)		
Sex					
Male	19(14.4)	113(85.6)	132(100.0)	13.220	0.001*
Female	107(30.7)	241(69.3)	348(100.0)		
Religion					
Christianity	118(28.0)	304(72.0)	422(100.0)	5.388	0.068
Islam	8(14.0)	49(86.0)	57(100.0)		
Traditional	0(0.0)	1(100.0)	1(100.0)		
Education					
Primary	4(80.0)	1(20.0)	5(100.0)	9.056	0.029*
Secondary	15(32.6)	31(67.4)	46(100.0)		
Tertiary	91(25.4)	267(74.6)	358(100.0)		
Postgraduate	16(22.5)	55(77.5)	71(100.0)		
Marital status					
Never married	23(30.3)	53(69.7)	76(100.0)	6.710	0.152

Currently married	103(26.6)	284(73.4)	387(100.0)		
Widowed	0(0.0)	11(100.0)	11(100.0)		
Divorced	0(0.0)	1(100.0)	1(100.0)		
Separated	0(0.0)	5(100.0)	5(100.0)		
Grade level					
2-7	42(36.5)	73(63.5)	115(100.0)	11.298	0.004*
8-12	69(25.4)	203(74.6)	272(100.0)		
13-17	15(16.1)	78(83.9)	93(100.0)		

*P<0.05

Table 4 shows the association between knowledge about modifiable risk factors for hypertension and their Age, sex, religion, education, marital status, and grade level. Their knowledge is significant with their age, sex, education, and grade level because the p-value for each of the socio-demographic characteristics was less than 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between attitude and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

	ATTITUDE SCORE			Chi-Square	P-Value
	Positive	Negative	Total		
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		
Age					
<30	36(40.0)	54(60.0)	90(100.0)	0.242	0.886
30-39	59(36.9)	101(63.1)	160(100.0)		
≥40	88(38.3)	142(61.7)	230(100.0)		
Sex					
Male	51(38.6)	81(61.4)	132(100.0)	0.020	0.887
Female	132(37.9)	216(62.1)	348(100.0)		
Religion					
Christianity	157(37.2)	265(62.8)	422(100.0)	2.123	0.346
Islam	26(45.6)	31(54.4)	57(100.0)		
Traditional	0(0.0)	1(100.0)	1(100.0)		
Education					
Primary	0(0.0)	5(100.0)	5(100.0)	4.633	0.201
Secondary	17(37.0)	29(63.0)	46(100.0)		
Tertiary	134(37.4)	224(62.6)	358(100.0)		
Postgraduate	32(45.1)	39(54.9)	71(100.0)		
Marital status					
Never married	31(40.8)	45(59.2)	76(100.0)	1.559	0.816
Currently married	147(38.0)	240(62.0)	387(100.0)		
Widowed	4(36.4)	7(63.6)	11(100.0)		
Divorced	0(0.0)	1(100.0)	1(100.0)		
Separated	1(20.0)	4(80.0)	5(100.0)		
Grade level					
2-7	40(34.5)	75(65.2)	115(100.0)	0.728	0.695
8-12	107(39.3)	165(60.7)	272(100.0)		
13-17	36(38.7)	57(61.3)	93(100.0)		
Knowledge					

Good	49(38.9)	77(61.1)	126(100.0)	0.042	0.837
Poor	134(37.9)	220(62.1)	354(100.0)		

*P<0.05

Table 5 shows the association between attitude towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension and their Age, sex, religion, education, marital status, grade level and knowledge. The result revealed that there was no significant relationship between attitude and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension because none of the p-values were less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is not rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between practice and socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

	PRACTICE SCORE			Chi-Square	P-Value
	Good	Poor	Total		
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)		
Age					
<30	43(47.8)	47(52.2)	90(100.0)	3.256	0.196
30-39	79(49.4)	81(50.6)	160(100.0)		
≥40	131(57.0)	99(43.0)	230(100.0)		
Sex					
Male	56(42.4)	76(57.6)	132(100.0)	7.725	0.005*
Female	197(56.6)	151(43.4)	348(100.0)		
Religion					
Christianity	234(55.5)	188(44.5)	422(100.0)	12.379	0.002*
Islam	18(31.6)	39(68.4)	57(100.0)		
Traditional	1(100.0)	0(000.0)	1(100.0)		
Education					
Primary	3(60.0)	2(40.0)	5(100.0)	0.896	0.826
Secondary	24(52.2)	22(47.8)	46(100.0)		
Tertiary	192(53.6)	166(46.4)	358(100.0)		
Postgraduate	34(47.9)	37(52.1)	71(100.0)		
Marital status					
Never married	30(39.5)	46(60.5)	76(100.0)	14.967	0.005*
Currently married	217(56.1)	170(43.9)	387(100.0)		
Widowed	2(18.2)	9(81.8)	11(100.0)		
Divorced	0(0.0)	1(100.0)	1(100.0)		
Separated	4(80.0)	1(20.0)	5(100.0)		
Grade level					
2-7	64(55.7)	51(44.3)	115(100.0)	0.567	0.753
8-12	140(51.5)	132(48.5)	272(100.0)		
13-17	49(52.7)	44(47.3)	93(100.0)		
Knowledge					
Good	63(50.0)	63(50.0)	126(100.0)	0.503	0.478
Poor	190(53.7)	164(46.3)	354(100.0)		
Attitude					
Positive	102(55.7)	81(44.3)	183(100.0)	1.089	0.297

Negative	151(50.8)	146(49.2)	297(100.0)
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*P<0.05

Table 6 shows the association between practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension and their Age, sex, religion, education, marital status, grade level, knowledge and attitude. Their practice is significant with their sex, religion, and marital status because the p-value for each of the socio-demographic characteristics was less than 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion

Findings from the study revealed that (26.3%) had good knowledge towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension. This is not in accordance with a study conducted in Nigeria by (Akinlua, Meakin, Umar & Freemantle, 2015) where about half of his respondents had good knowledge of hypertension. But consistent with findings from Aladeniyi, et. al. (2017) study among civil servants in Ondo State, where only 28% of those diagnosed of hypertension had good knowledge of hypertension. This study finding is much lower than the reported rate among university workers, 62.9%, (Vincent-Onabajo, Mohammad & Umeonwuka 2015). The wide disparity in the reports may be as a result of the quest for knowledge in the academic environment. This suggests that workplace screening should be mandatory and periodic practice among civil service workers in the state.

The findings of the study also revealed that more than half of the participants (61.9%) had average positive attitude towards modifiable risk factors of hypertension. This is consistent with findings from other hospital-based study in Enugu, Nigeria and Turkey where more than 50% of the participants adopted healthy lifestyle measures once they were aware of hypertension (Ekeh, et al., 2015). However, it is not consistent with finding of a similar study in sub - urban Nigerian community which revealed negative attitude and inadequate practice towards life style modification among hypertensive patients where up to 81.5% use much table salt, 21.3% eat vegetables regularly with only 9.3% engaging in exercise (Mill, et al., 2016). This may be due to differences in the study area, in which there is more enlightenment by health workers in hospital based urban study area. However, it was revealed from the findings that (52.7%) had average good practice towards modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

Conclusions

The researcher concluded that respondents had poor knowledge, average positive attitude and average good practices toward hypertension. Poor knowledge due to lack of quality information on hypertension may likely be responsible for the average life style modification they lived.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Measures should be taken by health providers to improve the knowledge and practice towards hypertension of this study population. Appropriate interventions need to be developed and implemented to reduce the preventable burden of hypertension
2. There is need to encourage health services including health education targeting various modifiable risk factors and promotion of good attitude and practices towards modifiable risk factors of hypertension.

3. There is a need to implement effective workplace health policy and regularly organise health education and screening for civil servants in the setting to reduce the burden of undiagnosed hypertension as a result of ignorance.
4. The health workers have to play part by educating the people and also themselves being an example in avoiding the modifiable risk factors for hypertension like consumption of fatty food, alcohol and smoking.

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